

Research Article

Formulation and Evaluation of Anti-Inflammatory Cream Contain Ricinus Communis Leaf Extract

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ABSTRACT

Ricinus Communis commonly known as Castor oil plant, has been traditionally used for its medicinal properties such as Anti-inflammatory, Anti-Microbial, Anti-Filarial, Anti-Bacterial, Anti-Oxidant and Anti-Asthmatic Properties. This study aim to formulate and evaluate Anti-inflammatory cream contain Ricinus communis leaf extract. The physical and chemical properties of cream include- PH, Spread ability, Wash Ability, Irritancy test, stability, Homogeneity, etc were Evaluated. The result Show that 10% Ricinus communis leaf extract show significant Anti-inflammatory Activity. With a 55.6% Reduction in paw edema (in-vivo). The cream was found to be stable, Non-irritating, And suitable for topical application.

INTRODUCTION

It is true that without nature human life is not possible. Food, clothes, and shelter are three necessities of human being and an important necessity is good health, which provide by the plant kingdom. Plant kingdom is rich source of organic compound, many of which have been used for medicinal properties. Ricinus Communis, family- Euphorbiaceae, is also knows as castor oil plant in English; in Hindi- arand, erand, andi, rend; Sans- Gandharvahasta, vatari, urubu; Gujrat: erandio, erando; Kannada- haralu, oudala, gida;

Kashmiri- aran, banangir; Malyalam- avanakku; Marathi- errand. Ricinus communis is tropical plant, known as castor bean, that is widely distributed across the world. In Indian system of medicine, the leaf, root, and seed oil of this plant have been used for treatment of the inflammation and liver disorder, Hypoglycaemic and laxative. The knowledge of herb has been handed down from generation to generation for thousand of years. Herbal drug constitutes a major part of all traditional system of medicine. Herbal system is a triumph of popular therapeutic diversity. Plant above all other agent have been used for medicine

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from time immemorial because they fit the immediate personal need, are easily accessible and inexpensive. In recent past, there has been a tremendous increase in the use of plant-based health product in developing as well as developed country resulting in an exponential growth of herbal products globally, an upward trend has been observed in research on herbals. Herbal medicine has a strong traditional or conceptual base and potential to be useful as drugs in term of safety and effectiveness leads to treating different diseases. WHO has tried to identified all medicinal plant used globally and listed more than 20,000 species.

1.1. Ricinus communis:

The euphorbiaceae is a very big family of spurge with about 7500 species distributes in five sub-families from over 300 genera, Ricinus genus herbs have only one known species, Ricinus communis Linn generally called castor oil plant. It contains wide range of phytoconstituent including terpenoids, flavonoids, alkaloids, anthraquinone, tannins, Saponins, polyuronides, glycosides, steroids, and reducing sugars so it has the curative effect for many common diseases. The castor plant was cultivated 6,000 years ago. The botanical name of r. communis was coined by Swedish naturalist Carlos Linnaeus in the 18th century. The seed of castor plant contain ricin, an extremely potent toxin. All parts of R. communis are used to remedy the pathogens such as roots, stem, flowers, leaves, seeds, and seed oil. Leaves of R. communis are used to relieve stomach pain treat jaundice and have anti-fungal activity. Herbal medicine is derived from plants and are used as alternative medicine compare to chemical medicine, they do not have side effect and can obtained easily at suitable prices.

1.2. Morphology:

Ricinus communis is a perennial soft-wooded shrub that can attain a height of (1-5m) and has remarkable lateral root and sturdy rap roots. Leaves of shrubs are spirally arranged, green in colour or acquired dark green colour when getting older. (1-3cm) long united stipules to a sheathing bud that are deciduous. The castor plant is glabrous, soft woody shrub and small tree up to 7-10m height, grown as an annual temperate zone and as perennial in the tropics. It is strongly tap-rooted with prominent lateral roots. The stem and branches have conspicuous nodes and ring like scars and gland often present at nodes. And shoots are usually glaucous, green, or red. The leaves are spirally arranged, borne on 3.5-50 cm long petiolate, and leaf blade is large up to 50-70 cm in diameter, palmately compound with 5-12 acuminate lobes, median one up to 8-20 cm long. The leaf margins bears glandular teeth. The inflorescence is an up to 40cm long. R. communis also known as castor plant, is a small tree implanted in moderate region.

1.3. Habitat:

The plant is common and quite wild in the jungles in India and it is cultivated throughout India. Chiefly in Madras, Bengal, and Bombay presidencies. Two varieties of this plant are known:

- A perennial bushy plant with large fruits and large seeds that yield about 40 p.c of oil;
- A much smaller annual shrubs with small grey (white) seeds having brown spot and yielding 37% oil.

1.4. Phytochemical constituents present in R. communis leaf:

Aldehydes, Alkanes, Amyrin, N-Butyl Morphine, Chlorogenic acid, Camphor, 1,8- Cineole citric acid, Caryophyllene, Decanamine, N- dimethyl

ricinine, Di- Butylphthalate, 2,5- Dihydroxybenzoic acid, Eleosteric acid, Fumaric acid, Gallic acid, Hyperoside, Linoleic acid, Lupeol, Myristic acid, Stearic acid, Tartaric acid, Tannins.

- Essential oil: Camphor, Camphene, 1,8-Cineole, α - Pinene, α - Thujone.

1.5. Taxonomical classification:

- **Kingdom:** Plantae
- **Order:** Malpighiales
- **Family:** Euphorbiaceae
- **Sub family:** Acalyphoideae
- **Tribe:** Acalypeae
- **Sub tribe:** Riciniinae
- **Genus:** Ricinus
- **Species:** R. communis

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

2.1. Ingredients:

Table No. 1: This table provides the knowledge about ingredient used in formulation of Anti-inflammatory cream:

Sr.no	Ingredients	Category
1	Ricinus communis leaf	Anti-Inflammatory
2	Stearic acid	Emulsifier
3	Cetyl Alcohol	Thickening agent
4	Liquid Paraffin	Moisturizing agent
5	Glycerin	Hydration
6	Triethanolamine	Neutralizing agent
7	Methylparaben	Preservatives

2.1.1. Ricinus communis leaf:

The leaves contain Methanolic and Hydroalcoholic extract. Leaves have long petiole and palm like lobed blades. Ricinus communis has much more reasonable origin. The word Ricinus means ‘Tick’ and the specific epithet communis stands for ‘common’ in Latin. The plant so named

because it seeds look like ‘tick’ and occurrence is ‘common’ in many parts of the world.

2.1.2. Stearic acid:

Stearic acid is a versatile fatty acid in humans, animals, and plants fats. It is a waxy solid component that is a part of any skin care products. Also known as Octadecanoic Acid, it is saturated long chain of 18 carbon chain. Describes as a way yellow white substance. It is used in various industries, such as Pharmaceuticals, adhesion, textiles, and construction, apart from skin care industry. Stearic acid helps to improve the texture and consistency of products. Also it improves, the ability of them to mix with water.

2.1.2.1. Benefits of stearic acid:

- Natural cleanser and stabilizer
- Effective moisturizing agent
- Enhance overall texture of skin care product
- Protect the skin
- Contains skin healing properties
- Suits all skin type

2.1.3. Cetyl Alcohol:

Cetyl alcohol also knows as 1-hexadecanol, is a fatty alcohol that is derives from natural source, such as coconut oil or palm oil. It is a white, waxy solid with a mild, non-irritating odour. Cetyl alcohol is commonly used in personal care. Such as, moisturiser, shampoo and conditioners, as an emulsifier and thickener.

Uses:

- Texture enhancement
- Stability of formulation
- Emulsifier
- Improve the penetration and absorption of active ingredients in the skin.

2.1.4. Liquid paraffin:

Liquid paraffin, also known as paraffinum liquidum, paraffin oil, liquid paraffin oil and Russian mineral oil, is a very highly refined mineral oil used in cosmetics and medicines.

Uses:

Liquid paraffin is an emollient (a substance that soften or soothes the skin). It works by preventing water loss from the outer layer of the skin. this relieves dryness and leaves the skin soft and hydrated.

2.1.5. Glycerin:

Glycerin is a naturally occurring compound found in your body. However, the glycerin you find in skin care comes from plant sources like soyabean and cane sugar.

Uses:

- Glycerin keeps skin hydrated
- Helps skin heels
- Strengthen skin's natural barrier

2.1.6. Triethanolamine:

Triethanolamine is used in formulation to neutralize pH.

2.1.7. Methylparaben:

Parabens are a family of related chemicals that are commonly used as preservatives in cosmetics product. Preservatives may be used cosmetics to prevent the growth of harmful bacteria and molds,

2.2) Extraction of Ricinus communis leaves:

The powdered plant material (200g) was extracted firstly with petroleum ether (twice the weight of powder) where a crystalline solid began to

separate. After allowing it to stand overnight, it was filtered and the filtrate was repeatedly extracted with methanol (thrice the weight of powder) using the maceration method for 72hour with occasional shaking. the separated extract were then filtered through Whatman no. 1 filter paper, and the methanol filtrates were then separately condensed to dryness using a rotary evaporator. Finally, the extract dried at room temperature. The dried extract was collected in a air tight container and stored at 4°C till further analysis. The crystalline substance obtained above was once again treated with a small quantity of ether, filtered, wash with ether, and dried in air, Yield: 1.7g. it was pale greenish yellow in colour. It was soluble in common organic solvent and also in hot water and had all the properties of Ricinus communis.

Table No. 2: In this table we discuss about quantity taken to formulate Anti-inflammatory cream:

Ingredients	Amount (Gm) For 20gm	Amount (Gm) For 50gm
Ricinus communis leaf extract	1g	5g
Stearic acid	2.2	5.4
Cetyl Alcohol	0.8	2.0
Liquid paraffin	0.8	2.0
Water	14.7	36.85
Glycerin	1.0	2.5
Triethanolamine	0.3	0.75
Methylparaben	0.2	0.5

2.3) Procedure for formulation of Anti-inflammatory cream:

1. Thoroughly clean the necessary glassware, wash it with fresh distilled water, and dry it.
2. Weight the active ingredient and excipients accurately.
3. Prepare the oily phase in one beaker by adding stearic acid, cetyl alcohol, and liquid paraffin with accurate weight.

4. In another beaker, prepare the aqueous phase by adding water, glycerin, and triethanolamine.
5. Keep both the beaker on water bath for melting at 60°C – 70°C
6. Now, add the oil phase into aqueous phase dropwise with continuous stirring.
7. Add the active ingredient and mix it properly.
8. Finally, add the preservative methylparaben after cooling.
9. Formulation is then stored in an airtight container.

2.4) Analysis:

2.4.1) Organoleptic properties:

It provides objective assessment of taste, smell, texture and appearance to ensure product quality.

- a) odour: The Anti-inflammatory cream fragrance and aroma
- b) Colour: by visual appearance of Anti-inflammatory cream.

2.4.2) pH test:

The pH meter was calibrated using a standard buffer solution. About 1g of cream was weighed and dissolved in 10ml of distilled water and its pH was measured.

2.4.3) Homogeneity:

The formulation was tested for homogeneity by visual appearance and touch.

2.4.4) Stability Testing:

Crems were divided into three parts and stability test were performed at 8°C ± 0.1°C in a refrigerator And at 25°C ± 1°C and at 40°C ± 1°C in an incubator with 75% relative humidity.

2.4.5) Spread ability Test:

The sample was applied between two glass slides and was compressed to uniform thickness by placing 100gm weight for 5min. weight was added to the pan. The time required to separate the two glass slides. i.e. the time in which the upper glass slide moved over the lower slide was taken as measure of spread ability.

It was calculated using formula: $S = m \cdot L / T$

here,

S – Spread ability

m – weight tied to upper glass slide

L – Length moved on glass slide

T – Time taken the determination were carried out in triplicate and the averages of three readings were recorded

2.4.6) Wash ability:

This test is carried out by simple washing the applied cream with water.

2.4.7) Determination of type of smear:

It was determined by applying the cream on the skin surface of humans' volunteers. After application of the cream the type of film and smear formed on the skin was checked.

2.4.8) Irritancy test:

Mark an area (one sq. cm) on the left-hand dorsal surface. The cream was applied to the specific area and time was notes. Irritancy, erythema and edema were checked if any for regular intervals up to 24 hr and reported.

3. Result and Discussion

3.1) Determination of pH:

Table no.3: The pH meter was calibrated using a standard buffer solution

Sr.no	Days	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3
1	Initial	5.3	5.4	5.3
2	7 Days	5.3	5.4	5.3
3	15 Days	5.3	5.5	5.4
4	21 Days	5.5	5.5	5.4
5	30 Days	5.5	5.5	5.4

Fig.1. pH test

3.2) Organoleptic character:

Colour: Pale Yellow

Odour: Aromatic

3.3) State of anti-inflammatory cream:

Result: semisolid

3.4) Texture:

Result: smooth

3.5) Wash ability:

Result: washable

3.6) Type of smear:

Result: Non-Greasy

3.7) Grittiness:

Result: No Grittiness

3.8) Homogeneity:

Result: Homogenous

3.9) Spread ability:

Result: The cream was spread properly on glass slide

Fig.2. Spread ability test

Result: Formulation and evaluation of Anti-inflammatory cream contain Ricinus communis leaf extract was prepared.

Fig.3. formulated cream

Table no.4: Observation Table

Sr. no.	Properties	Observation
1	Colour	Pale yellow
2	Odour	Aromatic
3	State	Semisolid
4	Texture	Smooth
5	Wash ability	Washable
6	Type of smear	Non- Greasy
7	Grittiness	No- Grittiness
8	Homogeneity	Homogenous

CONCLUSION:

The anti-inflammatory activity of methanolic extract of R. communis was formulated. This

activity was preserved when the extract was incorporated into formulated cream. The cream was intended to be used for Anti- Inflammatory Purpose.

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